

THE NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020: THE PERSPECTIVE OF STUDENTS WITH REGARDS TO THE CROSS- FACULTY APPROACH

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Abstract :

The Ministry of Education introduced the National Education Policy with an aim to transform the Indian Education system which will enable an individual to study one or more specialised areas of interest in detail and also develop character, ethical and constitutional values. It also aims a quality higher education which must enable personal achievement and enlightenment, constructive public engagement and productive contribution to the society.

Key words: C

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Introduction :

The current Indian higher education system has the drawbacks like;

- The large number of universities are resulting into low standard of under graduate education.
- Limited teachers and institutional autonomy.
- Rigid separation on disciplines, with early specialisation and streaming of students into narrow areas of study.
- Suboptimal governance and leadership of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).
- An ineffective regulatory system.

To overcome the problems and drawbacks in existing education policy, the higher education policy in particular, the National Education Policy 2020 has been introduced. Some of the major initiatives with regards to HEIs are as follows;

- Moving towards 'Multidisciplinary Universities and Colleges' with more HEIs across India that offer medium of instruction in multiple languages.
- Moving towards a more Multidisciplinary Under Graduate Education.
- Moving towards faculty and institutional autonomy.
- Governance of HIEs by independent boards having academic and administrative autonomy.
- 'Light but Tight' by single regulator for Higher Education.

The policy intends to have at least one large multidisciplinary HEI in or near every district by 2030. Further the policy aims for the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education to increase to 50 per cent by 2035 from 26.3 per cent in 2018. The Policy says that all 'Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)' shall aim to be multidisciplinary by 2040.

Objectives :

1. To study the NEP 2020 with regards to HEIs.
2. To study the perspective of students with regards to 'Cross Faculty Approach'.

Limitations :

The primary data was collected from the undergraduate students of colleges affiliated to University of Mumbai.

Research Methodology :

- Primary data was collected through the structured questionnaire.
- Secondary data was collected from newspapers, articles and official Government Policy

Hypothesis :

H_1 There is significant association between gender and awareness about the National Education Policy 2020.

H_0 There is no significant association between gender and awareness about the National Education Policy 2020.

H_1 There is significant association between gender and willingness to opt for cross faculty program.

H_0 There is no significant association between gender and willingness to opt for cross faculty program.

The New Education Policy and Colleges :

There are certain limitations that the college management may have to deal with while implementing the Cross Faculty Programme / Approach. Some of them could be as follows;

1. **Single stream or dual stream colleges:** After the implementation of the National Education Policy 2020, there is a threat for single stream or dual stream colleges to get phased out over a period of time. There will be no option for such colleges to move towards becoming multidisciplinary.
2. **Unavailability of desired subjects in multidisciplinary colleges:** There are chances that some multidisciplinary colleges may not have the subjects that students desire to opt for. Practically it is not possible for all colleges to have all the subjects of various streams.
3. **Fulfilments of requirements of working students:** The night colleges have been set up to cater the needs of working students. As per Cross Faculty Programme the students can opt for any subject/s from any stream. In case of non-availability of desired subject in their own college, the students can opt for the same from other college. The working students from the night colleges may find it difficult to adjust with day college to learn the cross-faculty subject.
4. **Coordination among colleges with regards to implementation of Cross Faculty Programme:** As mentioned above the Cross Faculty Programme allows students to opt for any subject from any other faculty. In case of non-availability of desired subject, the student may opt the same from any other college. In such

situation, there is a need of coordination between the respective colleges. Again, the colleges may find it difficult to coordinate with each other for the actual implementation of Cross Faculty Programme.

- Fear of unemployment:** The Cross Faculty Approach in the NEP 2020 clearly intends phasing out of single stream or dual stream colleges over a period of time. Such colleges have the only option to survive will be converting themselves to the multidisciplinary colleges which will be practically difficult for them.

Data Analysis and Interpretation :

Total 145 Responses collected. Out of total respondents 30.3% are male respondents and balance 69.7% are female respondents.

Figure No.1

Out of 145 respondents 47 respondents were from Arts and 98 respondents were from Commerce Faculty.

Figure No.2

The respondents were asked the question on awareness with regards to Cross Faculty Approach in the NEP 2020.

62.8% respondents were aware about the Cross Faculty Approach in National Education Policy 2020.

Figure No. 3

The question was asked about the feasibility of the National Education Policy 2020.

85.5% respondents were of the opinion that the Cross Faculty Approach of NEP 2020 would be feasible to implement in the system.

Figure No. 4

The question was about the generation of more and better job opportunities after the implementation of the NEP 2020.

86.9% respondents opined that the more and better job opportunities would be generated due the implementation of the NEP 2020.

Figure No.5

The respondents were asked that which approach / programme would be preferred out of Current Single Faculty Programme and New Cross Faculty Programme.

Out of total respondents 55.2% selected the Current Single Faculty Programme and 44.8% respondents selected New Cross Faculty Programme.

Figure No.6

Testing of Hypotheses :

- There is no significant association between gender and Awareness about NEP.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.053 ^a	1	.819		
Continuity Correction ^b	.002	1	.966		
Likelihood Ratio	.052	1	.819		
Fisher's Exact Test				.853	.481
N of Valid Cases	145				

Table No. 1

- 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 16.39.
- Computed only for a 2x2 table

Result

The Table No.1 indicated that for the variable awareness about the National Education policy 2020, calculated p-value is greater than standard p-value 0.05. Therefore, Null Hypothesis was Accepted and Alternate hypothesis was Rejected. It means **there is no significant association between gender and awareness about the National Education Policy 2020.**

- There is no significant association between gender and willingness to opt for cross faculty program.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.053 ^a	1	.819		
Continuity Correction ^b	.002	1	.966		
Likelihood Ratio	.052	1	.819		
Fisher's Exact Test				.853	.481
N of Valid Cases	145				

Table No. 2

- 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 16.39.
- Computed only for a 2x2 table

Result :

The Table No.2 indicated that for the variable willingness to opt for cross faculty program, calculated p-value is greater than standard p-value 0.05. Therefore, Null Hypothesis was Accepted and Alternate hypothesis was Rejected. It means **there is no significant association between gender and willingness to opt for cross faculty program.**
findings

Findings :

1. It was found that 62.8% respondents were aware about the Cross Faculty Approach in National Education Policy 2020.
2. It was found that 85.5% respondents were of the opinion that the Cross Faculty Approach would be feasible and convenient to implement.
3. It was found that 86.9% respondents were of the opinion that the NEP 2020 would generate more and better job opportunities.
4. It was found that 55.2% respondents were of the opinion that current Single Faculty Programme is better while remaining 44.8% respondents opined that new Cross Faculty Programme would be better.

Suggestion and Recommendation :

1. The New Education Policy 2020 has a student centric approach. Thus, it is required to make students and parents aware about the NEP 2020 especially with regards to Cross Faculty Approach.
2. To generate such kind of awareness among the students and parents, the Government should take initiatives through online or offline modes like:
 - Counselling sessions
 - Workshops
3. Teachers act as an intermediary between students/ parents and Government. Thus, the training and awareness programmes must be organised by the Government for the teacher fraternity.
4. The initiatives taken by the Government should be publicised and promoted properly through social media, news channels and print media.

Conclusion :

The fundamental principle of the NEP 2020 is Multi-disciplinary and a Holistic education across the sciences, social sciences, art, humanities and sports for a multi-disciplinary world in order to ensure the unity and integrity of all knowledge. The clarity, feasibility and outcome could be seen only when the policy would be actually implemented in the educational institutions. Further the corrective measures, if required could be taken during the course of implementation.

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Cite This Article:

**Dr. Eknath K. Zhrekar And **Dr. Anaya A. Markandeya, (2022). The national education policy 2020: the perspective of students with regards to the cross-faculty approach. Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, XI (II), 40-47*